

APPLYING THE INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS (IFRS) AND THEIR EFFECT ON THE QUALITY OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION IN THE FINANCIAL LISTS OF THE JORDANIAN COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to evaluate Applying the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and Their Effect on the Quality of Accounting Information in the Financial Lists of the Jordanian Commercial Banks. The study population consisted of (13) commercial banks, while the study sample consisted of the employees working in the commercial banks in the following jobs: Financial manager, Head of audit department, Head of accounting department in each bank, where the sample consisted of (505) participants. The results showed that there is a statistically significant impact for applying the international financial reporting standards on the quality of accounting information with its dimensions (valid representation, understandability, comparability, verifiability) in the Jordanian commercial banks. The results revealed that the total mean for applying the international financial reporting standards was high; this is attributed to the sensitive nature of the banks' work and the necessity of being committed to the latest globally-adapted standards and procedures in organizing their financial reports and confirming their transactions.

Keywords: Applying the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), Quality of Accounting Information in the Financial Lists.

Introduction:

The world witnessed a considerable growth in the various domains, especially in the economic and financial domains, which made it necessary to provide financial information that is easily understood and compared at the international level. Therefore, there has been an urgent need to reconsider the issue of multi-accounting systems at the international level by investigating the differences between them and attempting to keep the latter at lowest levels. This context required issuing accounting standards that were globally accepted, known previously as the international accounting standards (IAS) and known currently as the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). The international accounting standards (IAS) makes the accounting information more beneficial to investors for the purposes of prediction and evaluation. Also, the disclosed profits are more expressive of the low performance of companies, especially those outside the regional borders, where investors seek investment opportunities outside their countries. Therefore, the board of international accounting standards aimed to achieve the international accounting unity.

The International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and its interpretations are issued by the board of international accounting standards (IAS), where those standards aim to develop a high quality package of accounting standards that are understandable and applicable to the

participants in the international capital market and other users to make right economic decisions (Eminick, 2017) .

The accounting information issued by the accounting system should have a high quality according to the qualitative characteristics of accounting information, so that stakeholders can adopt them in making the various decisions based on the need of each of them. Also, accounting information is considered as an important production element that has an important role in determining the effectiveness of facilities. Therefore, those facilities aimed at designing and building developed systems in order to control the considerable amount of information necessary for the management of facilities.

Several studies revealed that converting to the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) will contribute to achieving many advantages and benefits for the accounting institution. Despite that, there is still controversy among academicians concerning the extent to which the international financial standards adopt the various accounting systems between countries, especially when those standards were developed to suit the requirements of capital and free markets in the developed economics and countries.

The International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) are considered amongst the contemporary tools in modern accounting thought, where they are mainly used to improve the quality of accounting performance in organizations in order to achieve the core objectives of the accounting system. They were also described as a response for the increased strategic role for the accounting profession with regard to supporting competitiveness and strategic success among organizations in the light of the ramifications of international and financial crises and their adverse consequences on the reality and future of economics in the developing countries. Based on the pre-mentioned, the researcher assumes that applying the international standards to prepare the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) affects the quality of accounting information in the financial lists of the Jordanian commercial banks.

The study importance:

The continuous advancement in business sector resulted in the emergence of new topics that require more pursuit by the accounting thought. In order to respond to the modern international economic changes, the accounting rules and systems should be developed, so that their outcomes can be used by clients inside and outside the organization; therefore, such information should be issued with an acceptable-quality level.

The researcher attempted to display and discuss the experimental and cognitive contributions in his domain of specialty by reviewing the relevant previous studies. The study importance is also manifested in its practical dimension related to the researcher's attempt to investigate the impact of applying the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) on the quality of accounting information with its dimensions (relevance, valid representation, understandability, comparability, verifiability, timeliness) in Amman stock exchange, and then analyzing the data interpreted by those standards concerning the level of variance in the quality of information, in order to come up with the conclusion and recommendations that serve the interest of the

investigated banks for the implementation of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) to improve the performance of the accounting system.

The study objectives:

The current study aimed at achieving the following objectives:

First, investigating the impact of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) on improving the quality of accounting information with its dimensions (valid representation, understandability, comparability, verifiability).

Second, verifying the level of awareness among banking departments and those benefiting from the banks of the private sector concerning the importance and advantages of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) .

Third, displaying and discussing the cognitive contributions relating to the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) .

The theoretical framework:

Sang-GiunYim (2020) conducted a study which confirmed that the mandatory adoption of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in relation to cost of the rights of banking property improves the quality of accounting information which, in turn, reduce the cost of property rights. The results revealed that the cost of the property rights in banks increases after adopting the International Financial Reporting Standards in the countries with strong banking sector. Also, adopting those standards will increase the cost of banks' shares in the countries with strong banking stakeholders.

Yasas and Pereira (2019) conducted a study which aimed at investigating the impact of International Financial Reporting Standards on the quality of accounting information in terms of the suitable value for the manufacturing companies enlisted in Colombo stock exchange. The results revealed that the importance of the value of accounting information didn't improve noticeably after the implementation of the International Financial Reporting Standards. The study recommended the necessity of conducting further studies in this domain by using a larger sample that covers the various sectors in Colombo stock exchange for a longer period of time in order to investigate the different indices of accounting information and verify the impact of adopting the International Financial Reporting Standards on the quality of accounting information.

Muyiwa (2018) conducted a study which aimed at identifying the impact of adopting the International Financial Reporting Standards on the extent of importance of the information issued by the companies enlisted in the Nigerian stock exchange as well as the extent to which the companies enlisted in the Nigerian stock exchange are committed to the International Financial Reporting Standards. The results revealed that adopting the International Financial Reporting Standards had a positive impact on improving the information in the list of financial position and income list.

Yusrina and Mukhtaruddin (2017) conducted a study which aimed at identifying whether there is an increase in the quality of financial reports after the convergence of the International Financial Reporting Standards in 2012 in Indonesia. The results revealed that there had been more improved quality in the financial reports after the increased convergence of the International Financial Reporting Standards, and that there was more value for the profit management after the convergence of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). The results also revealed that there is a negative relationship between the size of the company and the level of profit management; i.e. the larger the company, the higher level of profit management will be. The results also revealed that there is an inverse relationship between the impact of the total fixed assets on the engagement level in profit management, which means that the companies with higher total fixed assets will be less engaged in practicing profit management; it also means that the higher the value of financial leverage in the company, the higher the value of the activities of profit management will be.

Balea (2013) conducted a study which aimed at identifying the impact of adopting the International Financial Reporting Standards in Europe on the quality of financial reports from the perspective of relevance value and focused on the European experience that delegated all the trading companies in the Union market with the role of determining the quality of financial reports. The results revealed that the differences between countries in accounting organization may still exist after adopting the International Financial Reporting Standards.

Poulso and Leventis (2013) conducted a study which aimed at demonstrating the impact of applying the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) on the quality of accounting information in the Greek environment. The results revealed that applying the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) contributed to reducing the practices of profit management. Based on the implementation of these standards, losses are acknowledged in the suitable time with the increase in the relevance value of the accounting numbers as compared with the standards of local accounting.

The study hypotheses:

The main hypothesis:

H₀: there is no statistically significant impact at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for applying the International Financial Reporting Standards on the quality of accounting information with its dimensions (valid representation, understandability, comparability, verifiability) in the Jordanian commercial banks.

The study methodology:

In order to achieve the study objectives, the researcher used the analytical descriptive approach, which is known a method that addresses events, phenomena and practices that exist and available for study and measurement without intervention in their procedures. The researcher can interact with them in terms of description and analysis. The study aimed to apply the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and their effect on the quality of accounting

information in the financial lists for the Jordanian commercial banks in order to reach the best results with the least costs and effort. The study used two basic types of data:

The primary data: the study addressed the field domain by distributing questionnaires to investigate some research elements and collect the required data related to the study topic, and then unload and analyze them.

The secondary data: Thebooks, annual periodics, and publications relevant to the study topic were reviewed.

The study population:

The study population consisted of (13) commercial banks, while the study sample consisted of the employees working in the commercial banks in the following jobs: Financial manager, Head of audit department, Head of accounting department in each bank, where the sample consisted of (505) participants. The questionnaire was distributed by hand by the researcher to all the sample. (404) questionnaires were returned and after reviewing the questionnaires, (22) of them were excluded due to incomplete data, where all the valid questionnaires with about (418) questionnaires were used in the statistical analysis using (SPSS).

Table 1: The names of banks

No	Bank Name
1	Bank of Jordan
2	The Housing Bank for Trade and Finance
3	Jordan Kuwait Bank
4	Arab Jordan Investment Bank
5	Jordan Commercial Bank
6	Investment bank
7	Arab Banking Corporation / Jordan
8	Etihad Bank
9	SocieteGenerale de Banque / Jordan
10	Capital Bank of Jordan
	Total

Displaying the results:

In order to test the study hypotheses, the researcher calculated the value of means and standard deviations for the responses of the study sample individuals in the items related to the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), where the mean was (3.888) with a standard deviation of (1.050). The results revealed that the mean value for the responses of the study sample individuals was higher than the assumed mean which, in turn, indicates the effect of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) on the quality of accounting information with their dimensions (valid representation, understandability, comparability, verifiability). The results revealed that all the mean values for the dependent variable (the

quality of accounting information) were high, with an average mean of (4.01); indicating that the attitude of the study sample individuals towards these statements are in the positive direction.

The results of testing hypotheses:

In order to test the study hypotheses, simple linear regression was used, and the results were as follows:

First, the results of testing the main hypothesis which stated " H0: there is no statistically significant impact at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for applying the International Financial Reporting Standard on the quality of accounting information with its dimensions (valid representation, understandability, comparability, verifiability) in the Jordanian commercial banks."

The model summary:

Table 2: The model summary for the dependent variable (the quality of accounting information)

R	R2	Adj.R2	Std. Error
0.569	0.333	0.329	0.454

Table (2) revealed that there is a positive relationship between implementing the international financial reporting standards and the quality of accounting information with their dimensions (valid representation, understandability, comparability, verifiability) in the Jordanian commercial banks, where the correlation coefficient was (0.569). The results revealed that the value of determination coefficient was (0.333), which indicates that the independent variable applying the international financial reporting standards accounted for (33.3%) of variance in the dependant variable (the quality of accounting information) with its dimensions.

Analysis of Variance

Table 3: Analysis of variance for the dependant variable, the quality of accounting information

	Total squares	Df	Mean squares	f	Sig
Regression	9.960		9.882	48.730	.000
Error coefficient	19.7676		.208		
Total	29.749				

Regression coefficients

Table 4: Regression coefficients for the dependent variable, the quality of accounting information

	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig
Constant	2.098	.296		7.042	.000
Applying the international financial reporting standards	.531	.075	.576	6.981	.000

The above table related to the coefficients of regression model revealed that t-value was (6.981) at a significance level of (0.000), which means rejecting the null hypothesis stating that there is no statistically significant impact at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for applying the International Financial Reporting Standards on the quality of accounting information with its dimensions (valid representation, understandability, comparability, verifiability) in the Jordanian commercial banks, and accepting the alternative hypothesis stating that:

There is a statistically significant impact at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for applying the International Financial Reporting Standards on the quality of accounting information with its dimensions (relevance, valid representation, understandability, comparability, verifiability, timeliness) in the Jordanian commercial banks.

The results also revealed that the regression slope was (0.531). Therefore, we can interpret that based on the fact that the existence of accounting knowledge concerning the importance of applying the international financial reporting standards among the employees of the Jordanian commercial banks, including accountants and administrators, will considerably contribute to supporting the ability of the investigated banks in applying the international financial reporting standards by understanding the application requirements that accounting knowledge achieves to the developers of financial reports. Doing so, increases the quality of accounting information, promotes its efficiency and enhances the application of the international financial reporting standards which, in turn, affects the quality of accounting information with its dimensions (valid representation, understandability, comparability, verifiability) included in the financial lists of the Jordanian commercial banks.

Discussing the results:

By displaying the data and testing the hypotheses, the study concluded with the following results:

The results showed that there is a statistically significant impact for applying the international financial reporting standards on the quality of accounting information with its dimensions (valid representation, understandability, comparability, verifiability) in the Jordanian commercial banks. The results revealed that the total mean for applying the international financial reporting standards was high; this is attributed to the sensitive nature of the banks' work and the necessity of being committed to the latest globally-adapted standards and

procedures in organizing their financial reports and confirming their transactions. The total mean was (3.899) with a standard deviation of (1.050), which means that the change in one unit of the independent variable will have a similar- degree effect on the quality of accounting information.

This finding agrees with (Muyiwa, 2018), (Balea, 2013) and (Poulos and Leventis, 2013) which revealed that there is a statistically significant impact for adopting the international financial reporting standards (IFRS) on the quality of accounting information. However, the results disagreed with (Sang- GiunYim, 2020) and (Yasas and Pereira, 2019) which suggested that applying the international financial reporting standards did not affect the quality of accounting information.

Recommendations:

In the light of the results, the study recommended the following:

- 1- The necessity of conducting further researches related to the international financial reporting standards (IFRS).
- 2- Pursuing the international developments that constantly take place to the international financial reporting standards.
- 3- The necessity of promoting the accounting knowledge of the human abilities in order to reach human resources that are adaptable with the requirements of change towards applying the international standards.

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